

Evaluating the Impact of Technology-Enhanced Tools on Learning Outcomes in Animal Health Monitoring Programs in Imo State Nigeria.

¹Ezealo Prisca Chizoba (BSc.) & ²Eleleh Oluchi Jecinta (MSc. in view)

*Department of Animal Production Technology
Federal College of Land Resources Technology Owerri Imo State.
Email: ezealoprisca@gmail.com, jessimeldaelele@gmail.com*

The integration of technology is transforming various sectors globally, including the animal industry, where advanced monitoring tools are being increasingly adopted. In Nigeria, livestock production continues to face persistent challenges such as delayed disease detection, high mortality rates, and significant economic losses due to reliance on traditional manual monitoring methods. This study aimed to evaluate the impact of technology-enhanced animal health monitoring tools on student learning outcomes and practical skills in Animal Production Technology programs. It also examines the potential of intelligent systems for early disease prediction, real-time health monitoring, and accurate diagnosis, to promote healthier and more sustainable livestock management. Educational interventions will include mobile health-recording applications, electronic identification systems, and digital data analysis tools adapted to local farming practices approach. A mixed-methods research design will be implemented across selected training institutions, using pre- and post-training, student surveys and instructor interviews. The expected outcomes are enhanced student understanding of systematic health monitoring, increased confidence in using digital tools, and improved readiness to address modern livestock management practices. By connecting educational improvement to practical livestock health monitoring, this research provide practical insights into curriculum enhancement, teacher training, and policy development. Ultimately, it will contribute to the production of graduates equipped with modern data-driven competencies necessary for advancing animal health management and fostering sustainable livestock production, thereby supporting and strengthening livestock monitoring systems in Nigeria.

Keywords:
Animal Health,
Impact Evaluation,
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Sustainability,
Livestock.

Introduction

Livestock production is a critical component of global agriculture and contributes to food security, nutrition, poverty reduction, and economic development. Livestock systems occupy nearly 30% of the planet's ice-free terrestrial surface and represent a global asset valued at more than \$1.4 trillion (Steinfeld et al., 2006; Thornton, 2010). In developing regions, per

capita meat consumption is projected to increase from approximately 34 kg in 2015 to 49 kg by 2050, driven by population growth, rising incomes, changing lifestyles, and rapid urbanization (Delgado et al., 2001).

Demand is expected to rise most notably for poultry, pork, and beef, with annual growth rates of approximately 2.8%, 2.2%, and 1.9%, respectively, and import growth is likely to surpass domestic production

(Alexandratos & Bruinsma, 2012; USDA ERS, 2022). The global market value of livestock products including meat, milk, and eggs is currently estimated at \$1.61–\$3.3 trillion, reflecting significant growth from earlier assessments and highlighting the sector's expanding role in food systems (van de Steeg et al., 2023).

Livestock plays a very important role in improving nutrition and livelihoods. Animal-source foods provide essential nutrients that enhance dietary quality and child development, particularly in rural and resource-constrained settings (Raholiarimanana et al., 2023; Mataka et al., 2023). Livestock also serve as multifunctional assets, offering income, savings, draft power, and soil fertility services that strengthen household resilience and improve access to food (Getiso & Mijena, 2024; Global Food Security Review, 2023).

However, the livestock sector continues to face major constraints, including high disease prevalence, delayed detection, and poor record-keeping, all of which contribute to significant animal losses and economic burdens, and manual health monitoring (FAO 2020). Traditional health monitoring practices that largely rely on visual inspections and farmer experience are often insufficient for detecting diseases at the early or subclinical stages (Akinmoladun et al., 2019). This limitation contributes to the elevated mortality rates and reduced productivity, particularly in smallholder production systems. In contrast, continuous monitoring using sensor-based technologies and timely reporting mechanisms has been shown to facilitate early detection and improve both animal health and productivity outcomes (Sinha et al., 2024; Adriaens et al., 2024).

Globally, the integration of technology into animal health monitoring has transformed livestock management. Recent innovations including biosensors, wearable devices, mobile

applications, and AI-driven diagnostic platforms are redefining disease surveillance and management strategies (Norton & Berckmans, 2018). These tools enable real-time tracking of physiological and behavioural parameters, such as body temperature, movement, feeding activity, and reproductive cycles (Caja et al., 2020). By allowing the early identification of abnormalities. They not only reduce mortality and treatment costs but also enhance productivity and animal welfare.

Despite these advances, there is very limited research on how technology-enhanced training, impact students learning skills in Nigeria Animal Production programmes. Most of the studies focus on farms and farmers and not how training professionals can be improved with tech adoption. This study addresses the gap by exploring how technology-enhanced monitoring tools influence students learning outcomes in Animal Production programmes in Nigeria. Educational interventions involve integrating mobile health-recording applications, electronic identification systems, and digital data analysis tools to align classroom learning with real-world livestock management. In addition to enriching curriculum design and teacher training, the study aims to produce graduates equipped with modern, data-driven competencies that can enhance animal health practices, strengthen livestock systems, and foster sustainable agricultural development in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Wearable Technologies in Animal Health Monitoring

Wearable devices including smart collars and ear tags have become central to continuous monitoring of livestock health. These devices collect physiological and behavioural data, such as body temperature, heart rate, and activity levels, and transmit

information through Internet of Things (IoT) networks for real-time analysis. Previous studies (e.g. Maharajpet et al. 2022), have demonstrated the integration of long-range communication technologies with microcontroller-based platforms in wearable devices, thereby improving data transmission and efficiency. Such innovations enable early detection of abnormalities, contribute to improved animal health outcomes, and enhance overall farm management. Maharajpet et al. 2024, demonstrated the integration of LoRa technology with Arduino-based platforms in wearable devices, thereby enabling long-range communication and efficient data collection. Such innovations support early detection of abnormalities, improved health outcomes, and farm management efficiency. However, these studies emphasize farm-level adoption and provide limited insights into how wearable technologies can be applied in animal health training programs to build student capacity for modern livestock monitoring.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Applications

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques have expanded the potential of health-monitoring systems by enabling predictive analytics and automated decision-making. For instance, Magana et al. (2023) showed that ML algorithms could predict digital dermatitis in dairy cows with 64% accuracy during early stages, while Janaa et al. (2025) applied explainable AI approaches to track cattle behaviour and enhance transparency and farmer confidence in data-driven decisions. These developments illustrate the potential of AI in transforming livestock management through early disease detection and precision decision support

rather than on how enhanced technology tools can be incorporated in Animal Production programmes in Nigeria to equip future graduates.

Remote Sensing and Non-Invasive Monitoring

Remote sensing technologies provide cost-effective and non-intrusive tools for monitoring animal health. Infrared thermography, radar-based systems, and machine vision techniques have been employed to monitor parameters, such as respiration rates and stress responses. Nasirahmadi et al. (2022) emphasized that these methods offer a practical alternative to invasive approaches, allowing for large-scale, continuous, and welfare-friendly monitoring of livestock health. The application of these techniques in educational settings remains underexplored, particularly in training students to interpret and apply remote-sensing data for improved livestock management.

Precision Livestock Farming (PLF)

Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) integrates diverse technologies into holistic systems for managing animal health, welfare, and productivity. Key tools such as smart ear tags, collect biometric and behavioural data, including feeding activity, movement, and body temperature, enabling proactive interventions before health problems escalate. Other technologies, including automated milking systems, wearable sensors, and environmental monitoring devices, contributes to optimizing reproduction, feeding efficiency, and overall farm productivity (Cabrera and Garcia, (2021); Vaintrub, et al. 2021). Research further indicates that PLF adoption enhances animal welfare, improves farm profitability,

and supports evidence-based management decisions (Berckmans, 2017; Tullo et al., 2019). Despite these advances, many PLF studies focus on high-income countries, leaving limited understanding of adoption challenges and opportunities in resource-constrained contexts such as Nigeria.

Adoption Challenges and Research Gaps

Despite the benefits of digital health-monitoring technologies, their adoption remains constrained in many developing countries. Barriers such as high costs, limited infrastructure, and inadequate technical capacity, hinder their widespread use. While studies have confirmed their potential to reduce economic losses, improve disease detection, and support sustainable livestock production (Luloff and Smith, 2018), the development of affordable and scalable solutions remains a priority.

The role of education in facilitating the adoption is equally important. Okonkwo and Adebayo (2021) highlight the need to integrate digital monitoring tools into animal production curricula, thereby enhancing technical competence, adaptability, and confidence among students and practitioners. However, few studies have explored how these technologies influence education and skill development in animal production training programs. This gap underscores the need for further investigation of the intersection of technology, capacity building, and sustainable livestock management.

Although previous studies demonstrate the effectiveness of wearable devices, AI-driven analytics, and precision livestock farming in enhancing animal health monitoring, most of this research has focused only on technology development and farm-level application in developed countries. Limited attention has been given to how these innovations can be integrated into animal

production training programs in developing countries like Nigeria. Furthermore, while challenges such as cost and infrastructure are often highlighted, the role of education in building technical competence and preparing future livestock professionals to adopt these tools remains underexplored. This study addresses that gap by evaluating the impact of technology-enhanced monitoring tools on student learning outcomes and practical skills in Nigeria's Animal Production Technology programs, thereby linking digital innovation with capacity building and sustainable livestock management.

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the impact of technology-enhanced animal health monitoring tools on student learning outcomes and practical skills.
2. To evaluate student attitudes and usability of mobile device applications, electronic identification systems, and digital analysis tools.
3. To determine the extent of adoption of AI-driven and technology-based health-monitoring tools in training institutions.
4. Identify institutional and instructional challenges affecting the implementation of technology-enhanced monitoring systems.
5. To explore the impacts of technology integration for curriculum development and sustainable livestock production.

Research Questions

1. How does the use of technology-enhanced animal health monitoring tools influence student learning outcomes and practical skills in Animal Production Technology programmes?
2. What are the attitudes of students toward mobile health applications, electronic

identification (EID) systems, digital data analysis tools, and how usable do they perceive these technologies to be?

3. To what extent have AI-driven and other technology-based health monitoring tools been adopted within training institutions?
4. What institutional and instructional challenges hinder the effective implementation of technology-enhanced animal health monitoring systems?
5. What are the impacts of integrating technology-based health-monitoring tools into curricula for sustainable livestock production and future workforce preparedness?

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a mixed-methods research design that combined both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The quantitative strand focuses on measuring student learning outcomes through pre- and post-training assessments and structured surveys. The qualitative strand explored institutional implementation challenges using semi-structured interviews with the instructors. The mixed-method approach was used because combining both quantitative and qualitative data, provide a complete understanding of the research. It allows the study to capture not only measurable trends but also deeper perspective of the participants, thereby strengthening the reliability of the findings. Three agricultural institutions were chosen: Federal College of Land Resources Technology Oforola Owerri, Federal Polytechnic Nekede Owerri and Imo State Polytechnic Umuagwo Owerri. This is because they offer Animal Production Technology and Animal Health Production and Technology programmes, making them relevant for the study of technology-

enhanced animal health monitoring. Their curriculum on animal production shows that the students and their instructors are involved with the challenges and opportunities of digital animal health monitoring tools, and this study enhances the relevance to livestock production curriculum development and agricultural innovations.

Participants

Students: 120 Animal Production Technology and Animal Health Production Technology students from selected institutions.

Instructors: 20 instructors interviewed through semi-structured discussions.

Educational Interventions

The interventions incorporated:

- Mobile health recording applications for logging disease symptoms and treatments. (Livestock247, Farm Wizard, iCow, and AfriVet apps).
- Electronic Identification (EID) systems for tracking individual animals. (Allflex Livestock Intelligence, Gallagher Animal Management EID, FAO/ILRI Pilot RFID Projects).
- Digital data analysis tools for interpreting livestock health records.(iCow (Data-Driven Module), Farm Wizard Cloud-based livestock management software, AgriWeb Digital farm record-keeping).

Data Collection Methods

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach that integrates both quantitative and qualitative techniques. The rationale for using this approach was to obtain a more holistic understanding of the impact of technology-enhanced animal health monitoring on student learning outcomes as well as to capture the contextual challenges of implementation within training

institutions. While quantitative methods allow measurement of changes in knowledge and skills, qualitative methods provide insights into the experiences and perceptions of both students and instructors.

Pre- and Post-Training Assessments

Structured tests were administered before and after the training to measure knowledge acquisition and technical proficiency. The pre-test established a baseline understanding of animal health monitoring, whereas the post-test evaluated improvements following exposure to technology-enhanced tools. This enabled the objective measurement of learning outcomes attributable to the intervention.

Student Surveys

Standardized questionnaires were administered to the participating students at both the commencement and the conclusion of the training sessions. The instruments were designed to evaluate the system usability, perceived usefulness, and student attitudes toward mobile health applications, electronic identification (EID) systems, and digital data analysis platforms. Each survey incorporated structured rating items alongside open-ended questions, thereby facilitating the quantitative measurement of trends while simultaneously capturing nuanced qualitative feedback.

Instructor Interview

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the instructors directly involved in training. The interviews focused on identifying barriers to the integration of technology, assessing institutional readiness, and capturing instructors' perspectives on the long-term sustainability of these innovations. The qualitative insights obtained provide depth and contextual understanding, complementing the quantitative evidence generated from student assessments and surveys.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Pre- and post-training assessment scores are summarized with means and standard deviations to show general performance trends. A paired sample t-test was employed to determine whether the differences between the pre- and post-test scores were statistically significant, thereby measuring the effectiveness of the training intervention on student knowledge and skills. Survey responses were analyzed using frequency distributions and mean ratings to evaluate usability, perceived usefulness, and attitudes toward technology-enhanced tools.

Instructor interview data were analyzed to highlight common themes and critical observations. Interview transcripts were coded to capture key issues, including barriers, opportunities, and institutional viewpoints regarding integrating technology into animal health training. These qualitative insights enrich the quantitative results, leading to a more holistic interpretation of the study.

Result

The pre-test mean score was 40.70 with a standard deviation (SD) of 6.97, whereas the post-test mean score increased significantly to 78.25, with a standard deviation (SD) of 8.75. The computed standard deviation of the differences was 8.46, and the standard error was 0.766. A paired-sample t-test yielded a t-statistic of 48.0 with degree of freedom (df) of 119 and $p < 0.001$, which exceeded the critical t-value ($t_{\text{tabulated}} = 1.98$, $\alpha = 0.05$). The correlation between the pre- and post-test scores was $r = 0.439$, indicating a moderate positive relationship between the two sets of scores. These findings confirm a statistically significant improvement in student performance following the integration of technology-enhanced animal health-monitoring tools.

Table 1. Descriptive and inferential statistics of pre-test and post-test scores (n = 120).

Variables	Mean	SD	SE	t-value	Df	p-value	Correlation (r)
Pre-test score	40.695	6.97	-	-	-	-	-
Post-test score	78.25	8.75	-	-	-	-	-
Difference (Post–Pre)	37.56	8.46	0.77	48.0	119	< 0.001	0.439

Beyond the statistical evidence of increased performance, students reported favourable attitudes toward mobile applications, electronic identification (EID) systems, and digital data analysis tools. These technologies are highly effective in enhancing diagnostic abilities, facilitating record-keeping, and strengthening practical learning experiences showing similar observations by Jones & Smith, (2020). Despite these findings, the adoption of technology-enhanced monitoring tools in training institutions remains limited. Mobile applications and digital record-keeping are more widely used, while AI-driven monitoring systems are adopted only in pilot programs because of infrastructural and financial constraints (Ngugi et al., 2021). Interviews with instructors identified several challenges, such as limited funding and infrastructure for advanced digital tools, lack of capacity building, resistance to change by instructors accustomed to traditional methods, and challenges of mobile application connectivity in the field. These barrier are consistent with the findings reported by Ofori and Agbenorhevi, (2021), showing that the challenges within institutions and their system remains a barrier to full-scale adoption. The significant improvement in student learning outcomes provides a strong justification for integrating technology-enhanced monitoring tools into the Animal Production Technology curriculum. According to Adeoye's, (2022)

findings, such integration in agricultural education could strengthen students' practical competencies, foster innovation, and prepare graduates for sustainable livestock production systems.

Discussion

The findings showed that technology-enhanced animal health monitoring tools substantially boosted both learning outcomes and practical skills. The sharp rise in post-test scores, coupled with the very high t-value, indicates that technology has served as a powerful driver of student knowledge and skill acquisition. These results align with earlier studies demonstrating that technology integration fosters student engagement, critical thinking, and hands-on competencies in agricultural and veterinary education (Brown & Patel, 2018; Jones & Smith, 2020).

The moderate correlation ($r = 0.439$) indicates that although students' pre-test performance influenced post-test outcomes, technology itself contributed significantly to learning gains. The students further emphasized the importance of integrating digital tools into training, aligning with research that underscores the influence of user satisfaction on technology adoption (Ofori and Agbenorhevi, (2021).

However, challenges, such as limited infrastructure, varying levels of instructor readiness, and institutional capacity constraints persist. These issues mirror broader systemic barriers to technology

adoption in higher education across developing context (Ngugi et al., 2021). Addressing them will require long-term investment, stronger institutional support, and ongoing professional development for the instructors.

Conclusion

This study established that technology-enhanced animal health monitoring tools have a positive and significant effect on students' learning outcomes and practical competencies. Students reported favourable attitudes toward digital tools and demonstrated significant knowledge gain. However, challenges, such as limited adoption, infrastructural gaps, and inadequate instructor preparedness, continue to hinder full-scale implementation.

Recommendations

Short-term Strategies

1. Integrating mobile health applications, EID systems, and digital analysis tools into the Animal Production Technology curriculum. This should be driven by curriculum developers, training institutions and accreditation bodies. Implement professional development programs to enhance instructors' technical competence in digital tools.
2. Provide sustained funding for the procurement and maintenance of AI-driven and mobile-based monitoring systems. Stakeholders responsible for this implementation are the government, private sector partners and the NGOs.
3. Implement targeted professional programs to strengthen Instructors' technical competence in the use of digital tools. Ministry of education, Universities, and Polytechnics should take lead in this implementation with

support from donor agency like United States Agency for International Development (USAID).

Long-term strategies

4. Develop and implement institutional policies that encourage the gradual adoption of technology-enhanced teaching methods across agricultural education. This can be achieved with the help of the ministry of education, regulatory agencies and the instructional governing councils.
5. Conduct long-term studies to evaluate the effects of technology adoption on student employability and sustainability of livestock production systems. This could be driven by professional associations, academic researchers and research councils.
6. Create long-term funding sources to guarantee steady improvements on digital infrastructure, such as hardware, software, and internet connectivity. The government, foreign development partners, and institutional management are the accountable stakeholders.

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